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National Open Access Monitor: Dashboard Manager Application Form

Introduction

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This Dashboard Manager application process is carried out under the National Open Access Monitoring project, funded by Ireland's National Open Research Forum (NORF) under the NORF Open Research Fund 2022 to address one of the six priority actions of Ireland's National Action Plan for Open Research 2022-2023.

Context

The National Open Access Monitor will include dashboards for each RPO and RFO. As described in the OpenAIRE Inception Report:

<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10005955>:

Rights of National/RPO/RFO Managers:

Currently, the primary National/RPO/RFO Managers will enjoy specific rights, including:

- Access to the Sandbox.
- Access to OpenORGS.

We are discussing expanding these rights to include the ability to invite additional dashboard managers who will also have the same rights, via the Monitor admin.

However, it's crucial to note that for the purpose of maintaining organization deduplication, only one National/RPO/RFO Manager should have access to

OpenORGS. This ensures consistent and streamlined management of organizational data, avoiding any potential duplications or inconsistencies. In other words, the primary dashboard manager is the only one that can deduplicate, any additional managers they invite will have access to the Sandbox only.

Institutional Repository/CRIS Managers:

It's important to differentiate that the Institutional Repository/CRIS Managers who have registered with OpenAIRE PROVIDE constitute a distinct category of managers. Their roles and access privileges are separate from those of RPO/RFO Managers, they register directly via OpenAIRE PROVIDE and they have access to the management functions of OpenAIRE PROVIDE.

Dashboard Manager Application Process:

- please apply as the primary Dashboard Manager for your RPO/RFO using this form. Only **one** person may apply as primary Dashboard Manager for each RPO/RFO organisation/entity using this form. This data will be collated and validated by the National Open Access Monitor Project Manager (Dr Catherine Ferris) and supplied to OpenAIRE.
- following application and validation, OpenAIRE will contact you directly regarding next steps

As per the requirements of the project, this application process is open and transparent. The list of primary Dashboard Managers will be archived publicly on Zenodo. For respondents that choose pseudonymisation in their consent forms, identities will not be archived on Zenodo, but all of the information supplied in this form will be shared with OpenAIRE and with others in their organisation/entity on request.

Deadline

There is no deadline for responses to this form.

To view a reference PDF of this form, please click here [\[link\]](#).

Please note: all form data will be retained and hosted on a third party (Online Surveys) server and not on a MU server. For more information on how and why this form data is being collected, and how it will be managed, please refer to the **[Stakeholder Information Sheet and Consent Form](#)**. Your submission may be paused at any time by pressing "Finish Later". Respondents who click on the "Finish Later" link are taken to a page giving the form's closing date and a 'finish later' URL. This URL can be used to return to the form at the page on which you clicked the 'Finish later' link. The URL can be either bookmarked in your browser, or you will be asked if you would like the URL to be emailed to you.

If you decide to take part, you are still free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason and/or to withdraw your information up until such time as the

contributions are archived on Zenodo. The deadline to withdraw a submission from this form is COB the Thursday after your submission (in the case of Thursday submissions, the deadline is COB that same day). If you have any questions relating to this form, or require assistance in filling it out, please contact Dr Catherine Ferris (National Open Access Monitor Project Manager): catherine.ferris@mu.ie

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Consent

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Formal contributors to the National Open Access Monitor Project (e.g. through application forms like this) are required to complete and return a consent form in advance of contributing. This is a requirement of the Maynooth University Research Ethics Procedure. If you have not yet completed a consent form: stop here complete the consent form, available at [this link](#), return it to catherine.ferris@mu.ie and then return to this form.

Important: if the date/time of the form response **precedes** the date/time that the consent form is received, the form response will be immediately **deleted**. If you have completed the consent form, please select yes below and continue.

1. Have you completed the National Open Access Monitor Project Stakeholder Consent Form, and returned it to catherine.ferris@mu.ie? *

- Yes
 No

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Consent Disclaimer

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The National Open Access Monitor Project Stakeholder Consent Form allows participants to choose to be pseudonymised, if you would rather your contribution was not publicly attributed to you and your organisation/entity.

Due to the nature and purpose of this form, there are limits to if or how the information you provide in this form will be pseudonymised. If you have chosen pseudonymisation in the consent form:

- all of the details you provide will be kept on file by the Project Manager (Dr Catherine Ferris), for reference
- all of the details you provide will be shared by the Project Manager with OpenAIRE
- all of the details you provide will be shared with others in your organisation/entity (verified by email domain) on request, to enable them to contact you with regard to your organisation's/entity's dashboard on the National Open Access Monitor
- your details will be pseudonymised in the files archived on Zenodo

If you chose pseudonymisation in the consent form, and are happy to continue with this survey under these conditions, please continue.

If you chose pseudonymisation in the consent form, and are **not** happy to continue with this application process under these conditions, please **stop** here

and forward this form onto another person in your organisation/entity to complete.

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2. Your name *

3. Your department *

4. Your job title *

5. Your email address *

6. The name of the organisation/entity that you represent *

7. If you have chosen in your consent form for your response to be pseudonymised, please indicate which stakeholder group or groups you would like your contribution associated with for this purpose (e.g. Contributor 40, Research Performing Organisation 15). To note: if you have not chosen pseudonymation, any response to this question will not be actioned.

- Government
- Research Performing Organisation
- Research Funding Organisation
- Publisher
- Service Provider
- Other

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Submit Form

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Please click "Finish" below to submit this form. A download of your responses will be available to you.

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Survey complete

Response ID:

The form is complete. Thank you for contributing.
